

Prospective Randomized Trial of Sacubitril/Valsartan and Ramipril in Patients with HFrEF

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Abstract

Background:

Heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality. This study aimed to compare the safety, efficacy, and quality of life outcomes of sacubitril/valsartan (an angiotensin receptor-neprilysin inhibitor, ARNI) versus ramipril (an ACE inhibitor) in HFrEF patients.

Methods:

A total of 61 patients with HFrEF were enrolled and randomly assigned to either the combination therapy group (sacubitril/valsartan) or the monotherapy group (ramipril). Of these, 56 patients (29 in the combination group and 27 in the monotherapy group) completed the 12-week follow-up and were included in the analysis. Baseline characteristics, socioeconomic data, comorbidities, and echocardiographic parameters were recorded. The Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire-12 (KCCQ-12) was used to assess quality of life at baseline and at 12 weeks.

Results:

Sacubitril/valsartan demonstrated significantly greater improvements in ejection fraction, LVEDVI, and LVESVI compared to ramipril. Patients in the combination group also experienced a more marked improvement in both the physical and mental health components of the KCCQ-12 scores. Fewer adverse drug reactions were observed in the combination group, with rhabdomyolysis reported more frequently in the ramipril group. The most common comorbidity was hypertension. NYHA Class II patients were most prevalent.

Conclusion:

Sacubitril/valsartan showed superior efficacy, safety, and tolerability compared to ramipril monotherapy in HFrEF patients. It significantly improved cardiac function and quality of life, with fewer adverse effects. These findings support the use of ARNI as a more effective therapeutic option in managing patients with reduced ejection fraction.

Key Words: HFrEF, ARNI, Sacubitril/valsartan, rhabdomyolysi, ramipril

INTRODUCTION

Heart failure (HF) is a significant global public health issue, affecting an estimated 26 million people worldwide. Asia, which accounts for over 60% of the global population, has more than two-thirds of its countries classified as low- and middle-income nations. The rising burden of cardiovascular (CV) diseases in Asia is largely attributed to the increasing prevalence of risk factors like obesity and diabetes. As a result, the prevalence of HF in Asia has also escalated, with estimates ranging from 1-5%, compared to 1-2% in Europe and North America. In China, the prevalence is estimated at 4.2 million, while in India it ranges from 1.3 to 4.6 million. Unlike the West, where HF incidence rates have stabilized, the incidence continues to rise in Asia, with an estimated 500,000 new cases annually in China and another 0.5-1.8 million new cases in India. Given the region's large population and the evolving epidemiology of CV risk factors, Asia now has the highest number of people living with HF globally. Asian patients with HF tend to be younger and have worse survival rates than the global average. Additionally, there may be differences in the tolerability, efficacy, and safety of CV drugs between Asians and other racial groups, potentially reducing their effectiveness. A significant advancement in HF pharmacological treatment has been the introduction of a neprilysin inhibitor (sacubitril) combined with a renin-angiotensin system blocker, which has been shown to reduce morbidity and mortality in patients with chronic, symptomatic ambulatory HF with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF). In the Prospective Comparison of Angiotensin Receptor-Neprilysin Inhibitor (ARNI) with Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme Inhibitor (ACEI) to Determine Impact on Global Mortality and Morbidity in HF (PARADIGM-HF) trial, sacubitril/valsartan (ARNI) proved superior to the standard ACEI treatment, enalapril, reducing the risk of the primary composite outcome of CV death or first HF hospitalization by 20% and reducing all-cause death by 16%. The results of this trial led to the approval of sacubitril/valsartan by regulatory authorities in the US and Europe for the treatment of HFrEF and its inclusion in international guidelines

For heart failure, a condition where short-term survival is at risk, the potential cognitive side effects of chronic neprilysin inhibition were deemed an acceptable risk. However, for hypertension, which is a chronic condition that does not immediately threaten survival, this same risk of "mild cognitive impairment" was seen as a significant drawback. Additionally, the availability of many established, safe, and effective treatments for hypertension made the approval of sacubitril/valsartan for this condition more difficult.

Nevertheless, recent findings from studies on sacubitril/valsartan in heart failure have demonstrated that at the recommended therapeutic doses (100 to 400 mg per day), the clinical manifestations of neuronal toxicity are either absent or negligible. This evidence has prompted a reevaluation of sacubitril/valsartan's potential for hypertension treatment.

Myocardial infarction (MI), commonly known as a heart attack, occurs when there is a sudden blockage in one or more of the coronary arteries, which supply blood to the heart muscle. This blockage restricts blood flow, leading to oxygen deprivation in the affected part

of the heart muscle, causing tissue damage or death. The most common cause of MI is the rupture of an atherosclerotic plaque, which leads to the formation of a blood clot. Risk factors for MI include hypertension, high cholesterol, smoking, diabetes, a sedentary lifestyle, and a family history of heart disease. Symptoms typically include chest pain or discomfort, shortness of breath, sweating, nausea, and dizziness. If not treated promptly, MI can lead to severe complications such as heart failure, arrhythmias, and even sudden cardiac death. Early intervention, such as the use of medications like thrombolytics, or procedures like percutaneous coronary interventions (angioplasty), is crucial to restore blood flow and minimize damage to the heart muscle.

Method of the study:

- ✓ Neuropathic pain is a type of chronic pain that results from damage or dysfunction of the nervous system, sending abnormal pain signals to the brain. Nociceptive pain, which is often brought on by inflammation or tissue damage, is not the same as neuropathic pain, which is distinguished by abnormalities in the nerves themselves and sometimes described as burning, shooting, or electric shock-like sensations.
- ✓ Pregabalin is one medication that is commonly used to treat neuropathic pain. It belongs to the class of drugs called gabapentinoids, which work by altering the way certain neurotransmitters—like glutamate and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)—act in the body in order to modulate pain signals. It has been used to treat neuropathic pain in a number of clinical trials that have demonstrated the drug's ability to reduce pain intensity and improve functional outcomes in individuals with a variety of neuropathic pain syndromes. It has been shown to considerably reduce pain when compared to a placebo, making it the first-line therapeutic choice recommended by clinical practice guidelines for the management of neuropathic pain. It is generally well tolerated and also has analgesic properties. Peripheral edema, weight gain, fatigue, somnolence, and dizziness are typical side effects. These side effects, which are typically mild to moderate in severity, usually go away with time when therapy is continued.
- ✓ Because pregabalin is associated with a reduced risk of drug interactions than some other medications used in the treatment of neuropathy, it is a good choice for those with complex prescription regimens or multiple comorbidities.
- ✓ Neuropathic pain therapy needs to be done correctly to enhance patient results and quality of life. By evaluating the safety and efficacy of pregabalin, the research can develop

evidence-based therapy regimens that effectively lower pain and improve functional status, ultimately improving patients' overall health.

Methodology:

Study Site:

The study was conducted at a tertiary care, 1000-bed multi-specialty teaching hospital.

Sample Size:

A total of 61 at-risk patients were screened for the presence of heart failure. Of these, 56 patients were randomized into groups, with 2 patients from the combination therapy group and 3 patients from the monotherapy group withdrawing from the study due to reasons such as withdrawal of consent, infection, or death. The sample size was calculated using the Raosoft sample size calculator. For a random sample of 75 individuals with a 95% confidence interval, the required sample size was determined to be 65, with a margin of error of 5.75%.

Study Duration

The study was conducted from July 2019 to March 2020 at a tertiary care hospital. Data collection from human participants was approved by the institutional ethics committee under approval number VISTAS-SPS/IEC/I/2019/07. Informed consent was obtained from all patients in both English and the local language.

Study design:

The study protocol outlines the recruitment process, and it is observed that both groups' intention-to-treat analyses remain similar, given the small sample size.

Group A :

The sacubitril/valsartan will be administered 49/51 mg twice daily along with their usual medicines for 4 weeks in per oral form.

Group B:

Ramipril will be administered 5mg along with their usual medicines for 4 weeks twice daily.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients who have heart failure.
- Patient who are under treatment of sacubitril and valsartan as combination

- Patient who are under the treatment of Ramipril
- Patient with ejection fraction ≤ 40
- Patients willing to give consent for the study
- Patients willing to give consent for the study

Exclusion Criteria:

- **Who are contradicted with** sacubitril and valsartan and Ramipril
- Potassium level greater than 5.2 mmol/L
- Angioedema
- Systemic hypotension
- eGFR <30 ml/min/1.73m²

Elevation tests:

Electrocardiogram, Echcardiogram, serus creatinine, Blood pressure

KCCQ-12 questionnaire

Statistical Analysis

Statistical Analysis will be carried out with the help of SPSS with a confidence interval of 95%

Results:

A total of 68 patients at risk were screened for heart failure with reduced ejection fraction. Of these, 60 patients were randomized into groups. However, 5 patients from the combination group and 3 from the monotherapy group withdrew from the study due to reasons such as withdrawal of consent, aggravated infection, and death.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the trail participants

S.NO	Characteristics	Group A	Group B	P Value
1	Age(years)	64±5.8	69.2±4.8	0.8504
2	Gender (% male)	16(58.6%)	17(59.2%)	0.9732
3	Family history	12(44.83%)	11(30.72%)	0.8764
4	Alcohol	12(37.93%)	12(44.7%)	0.9892
5	Smoker	13(44.72%)	9(43.3%)	0.7985
6	BMI (Kg/m ²)	32±6.7	31.2±5.5	0.7923
7	Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	134.42 ± 26.08	146.81 ± 23.42	0.9458

8	Heart rate (bpm)	72.1 ± 11.9	73.8 ± 12.9	0.3443
9	Serum creatinine (µmol/L)	105.4 ± 28.4	98.2 ± 25.8	0.3408

Table 1 Shows the base-line characteristics grouping among the patients. The baseline characteristics includes age (in years), gender (% male), family history, alcohol, smoker, BMI (Kg/m²), Systolic blood pressure (mmHg), Heart rate (bpm) and serum creatinine (µmol/L).

Table 2: Gender distribution

SI NO	Group	No of patients(n=56)	percentage
1	Male	32	58.71%
2	Female	24	41.27%

Table 2 shows that among the 56 enrolled participants 33 (58.91%) were male and 23 (41.07 %) were female

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Table 3: Age distribution

SI NO	Age group (years)	No of patients (n=56)	percentage
1	55-60	17	28.67%
2	60-65	22	37.54%
3	>65	18	33%

Table 3 shows that the 56 enrolled participants 16 (28.67%) were in the age group of 55-60.21(37.54%) participant were belonging in the 60-65 age group and 18 (33%) were participant were belonging in the >65 age group

Fig 3: Age distribution

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Table 4: Socio economic status

SI NO	Status	No of Patients (n=56)	Percentage
1	Low income	14	26.98%
2	Middle income	26	47.21%
3	Upper middle income	13	25%

Table 4 shows that among the 56 enrolled participants 14 (26.98%) were in the low income. 26 (47.21 %) participant were belonging in the middle income and 13 (25%) Were participant were belonging upper middle income.

Fig 4: Socio economic status

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Table 5: Location Status

SI NO	Location	No of Patient (n=56)	Percentage
1	Rural	14	23.76%
2	Urban	44	78.78%

Table 5 shows that among the 56 enrolled participants 13 (23.21%) were from rural. 43 (76.78%) participants were belonging in the urban class.

Fig 5: Location Status

Fig 5 shows that the 56 enrolled participants 14 (23.76%) were from rural. 44 (78.78%) participants were belonging in the urban class.

Table 6: Co morbidity

SI NO	Co - morbidity	No of Patients(n=56)	Percentage
1	Hypertension	21	37.50%
2	Diabetes	11	19.60%
3	Myocardial Infarction	4	5.35%
4	Atrial Fibrillation	6	10.71%
5	COPD	5	7.14%
6	Cancer	3	5.35%

Table 6 shows the co-morbidity that is present in the patients who were enrolled in the study. The comorbidity that was taken under the study are hypertension, diabetes, myocardial infarction, atrial fibrillation, COPD and cancer

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Table 7: New York Heart Association Classification

SI NO	NYHA classification	No of Patient (n=56)	Percentage
1	I	8	16.072%
2	II	26	46.42 %
3	III	20	34.92 %
4	IV	2	4.32 %

Table 7 shows the NYHA that is present in the patients who were enrolled in the study. The comorbidity that was taken under the study are hypertension , diabetes, myocardial infarction, atrial fibrillation, COPD and cancer

Fig 7: New York Heart Association Classification

Fig 7 shows the NYHA classification that is present in the patients who were enrolled in the study. The categorization is based on the symptoms each patient express and are put under the corresponding category.

Table 8: Echocardiographic parameter – sacubitril/Ramipril

Parameters	Baseline	12 th week	P-value
Left ventricular ejection fraction (L VEF)	32 ± 3.6	37±3.1	0.3256
Left ventricular diastolic volume index (L VEDVI) ml/m ²	78.2 ± 4.2	72.1±3.8	0.2033
Left ventricular systolic volume index (L VESVI) ml/m ²	51.8 ± 4.1	44.3±5.9	0.306

All the values are Mean ± **SEM**

Table 8 shows among the combination group in the baseline and the 2th week where there was statistical difference all the three parameters that were taken into consideration. The P < 0.05 which is significant.

Fig 8: Echocardiographic parameter – sacubitril/valsartan

Fig 8 shows among the combination group in the baseline and the 2th week where there was statistical difference all the three parameters that were taken into consideration. The $P < 0.05$ which is significant.

Table 9: Echocardiographic parameter – Ramipril

Parameters	Baseline	12 th week	P-value
Left ventricular ejection fraction (L VEF)	32 ± 6.2	33 ± 4.9	0.6167
Left ventricular diastolic volume index (L VEDVI) ml/m ²	73.6 ± 5.5	79.4 ± 4.9	0.7972
Left ventricular systolic volume index (L VESVI) ml/m ²	54.1 ± 4.1	49.3 ± 6.0	0.5639

All the values are Mean ± **SEM**

Table 9 shows among the combination group in the baseline and the 12th week where there was no statistical difference all the three parameters that were taken into consideration.

The $P < 0.05$ which is significant.

Fig 9: Echocardiographic parameter – Ramipril

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Table:10 Development of Rhabdomyolysis

SI NO	ADR	Group A	Group B	P-value
1	Rhabdomyolysis	2	11	0.3458
2	Lightheadness	3	4	0.0783
3	Nausea	6	5	0.2638
4	Weight loss	2	6	0.6529
5	Skin rash	1	2	0.0972
6	Headache	3	3	0.0028

Table 10 shows the adverse events reported in this study. Development of Rhabdomyolysis is the most significant adverse drug reaction in group B while the group A showed a comparatively lesser development of anaemia.

Fig 10. ADR reported

Fig 10 shows the adverse events reported in this study. Development of Rhabdomyolysis is the most significant adverse drug reaction in group B while the group A showed a comparatively lesser development of anaemia.

Table 11: Quality of life (Qol) – KCCQ-12 score

Weeks	Group A	Group B	P-Value
0 th week	54.4 ± 10.6	56.16 ± 12.1	0.4891
12 th week	78.3 ± 7.6	69.16 ± 10.6	0.002

All the values are Mean ± SEM

Table 11 shows among the combination group in the 0th week 54.4 ± 10.6 in the mean KCCQ- 12 level while the 12th week showed 78.3 ± 7.6. The p < 0.05 which is significant. Among the mono- therapy group in the 0th week 56.16 ± 12.1 in the mean KCCQ -12 level while the 12th week showed 69.16 ± 10.6. The P < 0.05 which is not significant.

Fig 11: Quality of Life (QoL) –KCCQ -12 Score

Fig 11 shows among the combination group in the 0th week 54.4 ± 10.6 in the mean KCCQ-12 level while the 12th week showed 78.3 ± 7.6 . The $p < 0.05$ which is significant. Among the mono- therapy group in the 0th week 56.16 ± 12.1 in the mean KCCQ -12 level while the 12th week showed 69.16 ± 10.6 . The $P < 0.05$ which is not significant.

Discussion: A total of 61 patients were enrolled in the study and randomly assigned to either the combination therapy or monotherapy group. Of the 61 enrolled patients, 56 (29 in the combination therapy group and 27 in the monotherapy group) completed all follow-up visits and were included in the analysis. The remaining 5 patients withdrew from the study for unknown reasons. The study aimed to evaluate the impact of a neprilysin inhibitor combined with angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) as a combination therapy, compared to monotherapy with an angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor. The baseline characteristics of the subjects are presented in Table 1. Among the 56 patients included in the study, 33 (59.91%) were male and 23 were female. The higher number of males in the study can be attributed to their greater susceptibility to heart attacks, as shown in Table 2. The majority of patients were in the 60-65 years age group, followed by those over 65 years, with the fewest patients in the 55-60 years age group, as shown in Table 3.

The socioeconomic statuses of the subjects included in the study were categorized as low income, middle income, and upper middle income. The largest proportion of participants came from the middle-income group, followed by those from the low-income group, with the

fewest from the upper middle-income group, as shown in Table 4. Table 5 illustrates the geographic distribution of the participants, with the majority residing in urban areas, compared to those from rural areas. The comorbidities observed among the selected subjects included hypertension, diabetes, myocardial infarction, atrial fibrillation, COPD, and cancer.

Hypertension was the most common comorbidity among the participants, while cancer was the least prevalent. Since this study focused on heart failure with reduced ejection fraction, the comorbidities were predominantly related to this condition, as shown in Table 6. Table 7 presents the New York Heart Association (NYHA) classification, which categorizes patients based on their symptoms. Class I indicates no limitation of physical activity, and ordinary physical activity does not cause symptoms of heart failure. Class II refers to slight limitation of physical activity, but the patient remains comfortable at rest.

Ordinary physical activity leads to symptoms of heart failure (HF) in patients. In Class III, there is a marked limitation of physical activity; patients are comfortable at rest, but even less-than-ordinary activity triggers symptoms of HF. In Class IV, patients cannot engage in any physical activity without experiencing HF symptoms, or they have symptoms even at rest. There were more patients in Class II compared to the other classes, while Class IV had the fewest patients. Table 8 shows the echocardiogram results for the drug sacubitril/valsartan, indicating significant improvements in ejection fraction, LVEDVI, and LVESVI from baseline to the 12th week. Table 9 presents the echocardiogram results for the drug ramipril, showing changes from baseline to the 12th week, though sacubitril/valsartan demonstrated better outcomes. Table 9 also lists the adverse drug reactions (ADRs) reported during the study. Rhabdomyolysis, a major ADR associated with ramipril, was reported less frequently in the sacubitril/valsartan group. Other ADRs were minimal and manageable.

Quality of life:

The KCCQ-12 questionnaire consists of a total of 12 questions, with 5 related to the physical component score (PCS) and 3 focused on the mental component summary (MCS). The questionnaire was administered at the 0th week and again at the 12th week. Table 10 shows a significant improvement in both physical and mental health scores in the combination therapy group compared to the monotherapy group after treatment.

Conclusions:

There was a statistically significant difference in ejection fraction values between the heart failure patients in the combination therapy group and those in the monotherapy group. Sacubitril/valsartan showed good safety and tolerability in patients with heart failure and reduced ejection fraction. While ramipril is generally the preferred drug, it works more effectively and safely when used in combination, enhancing its potency. The two drugs work together to create a synergistic effect. The quality of life in patients showed a significant improvement in both the physical component score and the mental component summary after treatment. Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) were reported less frequently in group A compared to group B, with the more severe ADR, rhabdomyolysis, associated with ramipril, being more effectively managed in group A. Therefore, group A exhibited better safety and efficacy compared to group B.

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